

Fernando Perez-Oyarzun

Le Corbusier and Latin America: Urban Thinking/Urban Projects

Abstract

Le Corbusier showed an interest for travelling and for remote countries since he was a young student. Travels made part of his architectural education and later of his professional career, partially developed abroad.

Since his first travel to Latin America in 1929. Le Corbusier developed strong links with a continent, which he dreamt as an ideal setting for works and projects. On the other side, the master was a determinant figure in the process of reception of modern ideas on the part of Latin American architects. As a consequence of this fact, many Latin Americans were part of that crew of young architects working at Rue de Sevres 35.

The possibility of developing urban plans and projects was at the base of Le Corbusier's connections to Latin America. That fact motivated his first travel to Argentina, Brazil, Uruguay and Paraguay and also those he made the continent in the following years.

A series of urban proposals for Buenos Aires, Montevideo, Sao Paulo and Rio de Janeiro, sketched during his lecture travel in 1929 was the pregnant nucleus from which a series of urban plans and projects were later developed by Le Corbusier and some of his collaborators. Those plans were significant and influential both in the history of Latin American urban thinking and in its architectural culture in a variety of forms.

But Latin America wasn't merely a possibility of applying the ideas of the master and developing his projects. Latin American experiences left a recognisable imprint on Le Corbusier's biography and ideas. In fact some of his proposals for Latin America can be recognised as inflection points in his career and in the development of his ideas.

Trying to reveal the kind of connections established by Le Corbusier with Latin America: recounting the main episodes of that connections, mainly on the urban level, as their consequences on the Latin American scene; and finally, identifying the more significant inflections provoked by Latin America over Le Corbusier's ideas and biography, is the main aim of this presentation.

KEYWORDS

Le Corbusier; Latin America, urban thinking, urban projects

Fernando Perez-Oyarzun. Born in Chile in 1950. Degree in Architecture at the Universidad Católica de Chile in 1977. Graduate studies at the Universidad Politécnica de Cataluña, doctorate in 1981. Professor at the School of Architecture at the Universidad Católica Chile. He has been Chairman of the School of Architecture and Dean of the Faculty of Architecture and Fine Arts at the same university.